

Sexuality Laboratory Studies: Procedure of Human Sexuality Laboratory of University of Granada

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Adults are invited to participate in a laboratory study design to assess sexual arousal. Participation is entirely voluntary and with or without compensation depending on the funding of each study. Anonymity and confidentiality are always guaranteed. The dissemination of the study is through the channels of the University of Granada, local higher education centers and the research team using flyers, digital posters, email, and posts on social networks.

In the first phase, interested volunteers answer an online battery of screening questionnaires created on the LimeSurvey platform®. The battery consists of an informed consent to be accepted to participate, that include the objective of the study and what their participation involved, along with a Sociodemographic and Sexual History Questionnaire and the Spanish versions of the instruments to ensure compliance with the inclusion/exclusion criteria:

- a) Arizona Sexual Experience Scale (McGahuey et al., 2000) of Sánchez-Fuentes et al. (2019) to assess sexual function (i.e.,

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sexual interest, sexual arousal, erection/vaginal lubrication, ability to reach orgasm, and satisfaction with orgasm).

- b) Sexual Experiences Survey (Koss et al., 2007) to assess experiences of victimization during childhood and after the age of 14.
- c) Symptom Assessment-45 Questionnaire (SA-45; Davison et al., 1997) of Sandín et al. (2008) to assess different psychopathological symptoms (i.e., hostility, somatization, depression, obsession-compulsion, anxiety, interpersonal sensitivity, phobic anxiety, paranoid ideation, and psychoticism).

The inclusion criteria are: (a) being 18 years old or older; (b) having Spanish nationality; and (c) being cisgender. The exclusion criteria are: (a) having medical problems, sexual dysfunctions and/or psychological disorders; (b) taking medication that could interfere with sexual function (e.g., antidepressants, antihypertensives); (c) drugs/alcohol abuse; and (d) history of sexual abuse. Participants are assigned a code so that they cannot identify with the rest of their personal data. Eligible participants are contacted to schedule an appointment in the Human Sexuality Laboratory located in the Mind, Brain and Behavior Research Center of the University of Granada. The main reasons for not being cited are: (a) inability to contact them for the second in-person phase of the study, (b) appointment cancellation or withdrawal, and (c) voluntary abandonment. Participants are informed to refrain from consuming caffeine, alcohol and engaging in sexual activity, either alone or with a partner, during the 24-hour period prior to the experiment to minimize potential sources of variation in physiological response. Also, women are appointed two weeks after the previous menstruation to not evaluate during it (Suschinsky et al., 2014).

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In the second phase, in the laboratory, participants accept a second informed consent with the objective of the experimental task. The experiment is carried out in a soundproof and private room under the same temperature, lighting and humidity conditions for all participants. A man researcher for men participants and a woman researcher for women participants conducts the experiment. The researcher explains the experimental task, and the functioning, placement, and adjustment of the genital response recording devices. Additionally, the availability of an intercom in the room is indicated for communication with the experimenter in case necessary on the other side of the room. Subsequently, the researcher withdraws to the control room to ensure a correct recording of the psychophysiological signal, while the participants place the devices to record their genital response. Five minutes of adaptation are left before starting the experiment, during which participants have to remain seated with instructions to avoid moving, touching their genitals, and breathing deeply during the experiment. The experimental task consists of watching neutral content and sexual content videos that are presented while participants are seated comfortably. Depending on the study, the video presentation may involve either (a) a 27" UHD 4K screen (resolution of 3840 x 2160 pixels) while participants are seated comfortably at 100 cm from the monitor, or (b) virtual reality (VR) headset.

During the viewing, genital response is registered and at the end of each sexual film, participants respond to the Spanish versions of the Rating of Sexual Arousal and Rating of Genital Sensations (RSA and RGS, respectively; Sierra et al., 2017). A psychophysiological recording of a genital response is conducted. In men, changes in penile circumference were measured in millimeters using an indium-gallium ring (plethysmography). In women, vaginal pulse amplitude in volts was recorded using photoplethysmography.

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In the UHD 4K screen presentation format, OpenSesame, an open-source software for experimental research in psychology and cognitive sciences (Mathôt et al., 2012) was used to present the videos as visual stimuli (see Figure 1). Both the RSA and RGS were completed on-screen using a computer mouse, and the responses were automatically stored in an external file on the computer.

In the VR setup, a procedure analogous to the UHD 4K screen condition is followed (see Figure 2). With the Meta Quest 3® VR headset worn, participants use the VR controller to respond to the scales: the joystick moves through the response options, and the front button confirms the selection. Meta Quest 3® has a resolution of 2064 x 2208 pixels per eye. Before the main task, a practice trial is conducted to familiarize participants with the devices and the response process. During this trial, the researcher explains how to use the controller and asks the participant to practice responding to ensure they understand the procedure.

Figure 1

Position of the participant at UHD 4K screen presentation format

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Figure 2

Position of the participant at VR condition

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